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Ways for Promoting Academic Excellence of the Nigerian Child: Perceptions of Teachers and Parents

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the perceptions of teachers and parents about the ways for promoting academic excellence in the Nigerian child. Parents, teacher's and school administrators' involvement has been shown to be an important variable that positively influences children's education, particularly in the early stages of primary education. Various literature related to academic excellence of the Nigerian child is critically reviewed. Two research questions and two hypotheses have been formulated and tested in the course of the study. 200 respondents have been selected from Zaria local Government Education Authority/ Metropolis for the study. 100 head teachers and 100 parent have been randomly selected for the study, data, using frequencies and percentages for the research questions, chi IX¹) and t-test for the hypotheses, have been analyzed. However, the study revealed that all the seven ways on how to sustain academic excellence by parent and teachers have been affirmed by the respondents' tis some parent shy away from their responsibility at home. The paper however, concluded and recommended that parents, teachers and school, administrators must encourage students' readiness, interest and motivation toward teaming. Indeed; those involved in running of school should employ qualified teachers for better teaching and learning in schools.

Keywords: Nigerian child, teachers, parents, academic excellence, school administrators'

INTRODUCTION

The child's first and second educational, social, moral and physical experiences begin at home and school. It is in the family that every child is born, spends most of his early years and learns his mother tongue. It is later in life he goes to school and learn more social contact and experiences. It is therefore the responsibility of both parents and school administrators to guide and teach the child all the necessary acceptable norms and culture of behavior. In view of the forgoing discussion that many educationist and sociologist such as Dalta (1986), confirmed that all these early experiences have an

impact on the physical, social, moral and intellectual development of the child. In regards to early attendance to school, Noabuisi, (1988) Zhang and Carasquillo (1995). Stowiaezek (2009) and et al. recorded some studies in which there was a correlation between social class studies and early attendance to educational institutions. Thus, high social class parents send their children to school much earlier than those of low social class. This indicates that they know the benefits associated with education, indeed, Ogunsanya (2006) claimed that the early years of a child are the formative years and are of critical importance to the child, so it is the responsibilities of both parents and school administrators to prevention from putting up behaviors that can have adverse effects on his life and education such as late coming to school, examination malpractice, cultism, etc.

Statement of the Problem

The problem of "I don't care attitude" shown by some Nigerian parents, teachers and school administrators on the quality of education of their children have drastically led to the academic excellence deterioration in the country. For instance, examination malpractice has become one of the longest standing problems of our country's educational system, which the phenomenon has reached an alarming magnitude across the nation. Indeed, malpractice in examinations has become so rampant that hardly could any examination exercise or center take place without a sizeable number been caught in the act.

Therefore, one may anticipate that all this genesis and consequences of the menace of examination could be due to negative impact of academic excellence of the school children in Nigeria.

Based on the above factors and alarming conditions, this study was conducted to find the implication for parents and school teachers on academic excellence of the Nigerian Child.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study is to restore the concept of academic excellence of the Nigerian child from deterioration. Other purposes include the following:

- 1) To find out various ways academic excellence of the Nigerian child can be attained.
- 2) Determining the parental and teachers roles, in the development of academic excellence of the Nigerian child.
- 3) To recommend ways academic excellence can be disseminated into the Nigerian child.

Research Questions

1. What are the various ways through which academic excellence can be procured and achieved in the Nigerian child?
2. How can parents and school teachers enhance academic excellence of the Nigerian child?

Research Hypotheses

HO₁: Teachers and parents are not significantly different in their opinions or perceptions of the ways academic excellence can be attained in the Nigerian child.

HO₂: Male and female teachers are not significantly different in their opinions or **perceptions** of the parental roles in academic excellence and sustenance of the qualitative education in Nigerian child.

Significance of the Study

Certainly, judging the fact (hat the academic excellence of the Nigerian child is in degradation and shambles condition, then any study that could salvage the generations from the total collapse shall be a welcome idea to the following cohorts of the population: The parents, teachers, school administrators, stakeholders, academia, politicians and general citizen shall benefit from the reviving and restoring academic excellence of the Nigerian child.

Review of Related Literature

The review of related literature on roles of the parents, teachers and school administrators, are highlighted in view to .Ascertain ways of inculcating the academic excellence to the Nigerian child.

The Parents, teachers and School Administrators and the Child's Academic Excellence

In an article of law - study Aids Freud, S. 1924 in Dusek, J.B. (ed.) (1996), it was asserted that correct attitude of parent to education of children of early and pre-school age is positively reflected in their educational activities. In their own study on in what ways does parent's involvement affect children's academic excellence? Other studies by Eweniyi and Ogun Sanya, (2006), asserted that there is an increasing recognition Corinth developmental, educational and sociological theory that both school and home are important institutions that socialize and educate children. They cited the National Commission on excellence in education (1983), and in Academic Achievement - Family background and structure (2007) which claimed that;

Within the framework of home - school connections, much of specific debate and hope for change focuses on parents' involvement in their children's schooling several committees reporting on the nation's schools have fact listed parents involvement as a significant goal and target for educational reform.

Piaget and Kohlberg, L. (1982), claimed in their studies that "children who are excelling academically have closer and more mutually supportive families than persons from general population" At the end of their studies they confirmed that students who were performing successfully in school tended to have families who were emotionally closer. In another study by Amadi, (1986) titled "Academic Achievement Family Background and Structure" (2007) the writers confirmed that "A Mother does homework with her children. It is generally acknowledged that family environment is the most powerful influence in determining a child's academic excellence and achievement".

METHOD AND PROCEDURES

Descriptive survey design was used in the study in order to sample opinions from the selected respondents and generalize the facts on the entire population.

Population and Sample

The entire staffs getting to about four thousand in Zaria Local Government Education Authority are targeting population 100 teachers and 300 parents were randomly selected from Zaria metropolis in the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

Structural questionnaire was used for data collection 20 items on the various way| of restoring and reviving academic excellence issues and Imparting it into the Nigerian child tagged AEQ instruments were designed, 7 items on how to propagate and sustain academic excellence in Nigerian child tagged as PSQ were designer?.

Illustrations: AEQ = Academic Excellence Questionnaire PSQ = Propagating and Sustaining Questionnaire.

Methods of Data Analysis

Data from the research questions were analyzed by frequency counts and percentages whereas, chi (X2) and independent t-test was used in the analysis of the two hypotheses

Scoring Procedure

Four (4) point scale of strongly Agree (SA) (4) Agree (3), D.A Disagree (2) and strongly Disagree (1) was adopted. The mean of the scores was found as:

$$\frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = 2.5$$

4

RESULTS

Research Question One: *How academic excellence can be developed and achieved in the Nigerian child.*

Table 1: Depicts Analysis of how to Sustain Academic Excellence

S/No.	Identified Ways	F.N. = 200	% "	Decision
1.	Effective use of continuous assessment in schools	197.5	49.4	2.
2.	Effective inspection and supervision in schools	192.5	48.15	3.
3.	Changing attitudes of I don't care by parents and school administrators.	196	49	4.
4.	Parents and school administrators must encourage students readiness, interest and motivation toward learning.	200	50	5.
5.	Through the existing records such as good educational administrative text books.	193.5	49.7	6.
6.	Through interact, Television radio and newspapers.	200	50	7.
7.	Through the political wills to change the country's educational infra structural facilities including quality leaders.	194	48.5	8.

Hypothesis One

Male and female perceptions of the parental and school teachers' role in uplifting academic excellence of the Nigerian child were not significantly different from each other. The analysis is presented in table 3.

Research Question Two: The analysis of parental and school teachers' roles to enhance academic excellence and sustain it in the Nigerian child is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Depicts Parental and School Teachers Roles in the Sustenance of Academic Excellence

S/No.	Identified Ways	F.N. 200	= %	Decision
1.	School should hold meetings regularly to see ways of improving the; performance of students.	200	50.0	3.
2.	Parents should endeavor to pay the school fees of their children for the remuneration of the teachers and acquisition of teaching materials and facilities.	182.5	45.7	4.
3	Those involved in running of school should employ qualified teachers for better teaching and learning in schools.	199	49.8	5.
4	Government should address the issue of teachers' salaries and other fringe benefits very seriously.	19S	49.4	6.
5	Parents should monitor the movement of their children and quickly detach them from moving with bad peer groups.	200	50.0	7.
6	The school teachers should be able to continually monitor the learner's level of achievement and modify his administrative strategies accordingly; the learners are to get enough information of the state of his achievement relative to the objectives in order to be able to change his learning behavior.	192	47.0	8.
7	School teachers should encourage positive study habits of the students.	200	50.0	9.
8	Love your children and care for them educationally.	196	49.0	10.

Table 2 above, shown that parents and school teachers have various ways of inculcating academic excellence into their children.

Hypothesis Two

Perceptions of male parents and female head teachers on the ways of inculcating academic excellence in the Nigeria child were not significantly different from each other.

Table 3: Depict the Analysis of the Responses on the Perceptions of Male parents and Female head teachers about the Ways of Inculcating Academic Excellence in the Nigeria child

Respondents	No.	Negative respondent	Positive respondents	Marginal
Male	100	6 (42.5)	40 (57.5)	100
Female	100	25 (42.5)	75 (57.5)	100
Marginal	200	85	115	200

$$X^2 = \frac{\sum (F_0 - F_e)^2}{F_e}$$

X² = Calculated Value 18.5

X² = Critical

df = 1 under 0.05 alpha level of significance

The calculated X^2 Value of 18.5 is greater than the table X^2 of 1.92 under df 10.05 alpha level of significance. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis in favor of alternative hypothesis. Implication here is that male parent and female head teachers vary significantly in their perception of the various ways of academic excellence to Nigerian child.

Table 4: Depict the Analysis of the Responses on the Parental and School Administrators Roles on the Academic Excellence in the Nigeria child

Respondents	N	X	SD	CaL T	Critical t	DF	L.S
Male	100	1.45	0.82	1.71	0.98	199	s
Female	too	1.26	0.71				

Calculated t = **1.71**

Critical t = **0.98**

df = **199**

$$t = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

The calculated t is greater than critical t under df 199 at 0.05 alpha level of significance, therefore, the hypothesis states that male and female are not significantly different in their perception therefore one have to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Analysis in table I above shows that all the seven (7) ways on how to sustain academic excellence by parent and school teachers have been affirmed by the respondents. The percentage affirmation ranges from 193 (48.15%) to 200 (100%). Table 2 also showed that parents and school administrators have a lot of roles to play in restoring academic excellence from dilapidating in the country. Certainly parents were the first initiators of academic excellence. Analysis in Table 3 showed that the female and male teachers were significantly different in their perceptions over the various ways of academic excellences in Nigeria child. This finding was in consonance with the submission of Waker (2002), who opined that one of the most important functions of the family is to assist in taking the child through the stage of adolescence with the minimum anti-social behavior, so that the child's personality and intellectual development is not warped by an undue repression. However, Ojulari (2008), argued that in our society today it can i>e observed that many parents are not playing their roles properly. From experience in nursery, primary and secondary schools, pupils perform academically below expectation not because they are not naturally brilliant but because of the lapses from their parents or due to nonchalant attitudes of their parents toward their academic: performance in the school. As a result some of them do not pass entrance examinations to good secondary schools or enter secondary school with low academic standard. Table four (4) indicated acceptance of alternative hypothesis as there were different perception of the roles of the parents and school administrators. The calculated t was 1.71 as against the critical t of 0.95 under df 199 at 0.05 alpha level of significance. Therefore, the decision was to reject the null hypothesis. The finding agreed with Gail (2001) who posited that some parent shy away from their responsibility at home.

CONCLUSION

Generally speaking, the issue of academic excellence in Nigerian child is not of an individual issue but collaborative efforts. It evolves the hand of politicians, all teachers, parents, school administrators and general public to ensure that Nigeria child received an adequate knowledge that will benefit him and the entire nation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and discussions of research and observations made in the area where data was collected, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Parents, teachers and school administrators must encourage student's readiness, interest and motivation toward learning.

2. School should hold meetings regularly to see ways of improving the performance of their children.
3. Those involved in running of school should employ qualified teachers for better teaching and learning in
4. Parents should endeavor to pay the school fees (where applicable) of their children for the remuneration of the teachers and acquisition of teaching materials and facilities.
5. Government should address the issue of teachers' salaries and other fringe benefits very seriously.
6. Parents should monitor the movement of their children and quickly detach them from moving with bad peer groups.

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